

WATER AEROBICS FOR CHILDREN OF SENIOR PRESCHOOL AGE WITH IMPAIRED SPEECH DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract.

Abstract. Physical exercise is an important element not only for physical health, but also for mental development, like water and air. Water aerobics in particular has many benefits for a healthy lifestyle. This article discusses in detail Water aerobics for children of senior preschool age with impaired speech development.

Key words: water aerobics, speech therapist, speech development, psychological exercises, mental problem, etc.

From the etiopathogenetic point of view, children with underdeveloped speech form different groups. In some cases, this condition often has a constitutional character of genetic nature. Usually, the clinical picture of the defect in such children does not have serious psychopathological symptoms, especially psychoorganic symptoms. In other cases, signs of damage, i.e. psychoorganic and other psychopathological signs are clearly manifested. T. B. Filicheva described the IV level of speech development. Level I of speech development is characterized by the absence of commonly used speech, the absence of sentence speech (children without speech). Children at this level use simple words for communication, imitation of sounds, individual nouns and verbs in everyday context, simple sentences, and their sound composition is unclear and unstable. The child reinforces his "statement" with facial expressions and gestures. These children are characterized by a great initiative to search for speech in the process of communication and a critical attitude towards their own speech. At the II level of speech development - in addition to gestures and simple words, broken, but constantly commonly used words appear. At the same time, some grammatical forms are differentiated. However, this process is not stable, and the gross underdevelopment of speech is clearly expressed in these children. Children's narratives are usually poor and limited to listing objects and actions perceived by the child. Under the influence of special corrective education, children move to the new III level of speech development. This level is characterized by the presence of wide-sentence speech with elements of lexicogrammatic and phonetic-phonemic underdevelopment, which allows children to expand their speech communication with others.

Free communication is very complicated. The sounds that children can pronounce correctly do not sound clearly enough in independent speech. Undifferentiated pronunciation of sounds is characteristic, in which one sound is simultaneously replaced by two or more sounds belonging to this phonetic group. Now, at this stage, children use all parts of speech, use simple grammatical forms correctly, try to build simple compound and simple compound sentences. The child's ability to pronounce and repeat words with different syllable systems improves. Children have no difficulty in naming objects, actions, signs, qualities and situations

that are familiar to them from their life experiences. They can easily tell about their family, they can compose a short story. In oral communication, children try to avoid words and phrases that are difficult for them. Despite the fact that children use large-scale speech, they feel greater difficulties in constructing sentences than their peers with normal speech. Children with the III level of speech development have all defects in the pronunciation of sounds (sigmatism, rotatism, lambdatism). In the course of logopedic work, it is possible to eliminate the incomplete development of speech in many children, but in some cases this process was not effective enough, which required the separation of the IV level of speech development. Children with lexical-grammatical aspects of speech disorders and different levels of speech development are admitted to the logopedic groups for children whose speech is not fully developed. As a result of generalization of modern research data, some general and specific laws of speech desontogenesis can be distinguished. Analyzing literature sources, we came to the conclusion that underdevelopment of speech does not represent an independent nosological entity in the medical sense of the word. It is a collection of groups that are different according to mechanism, sign, system, weight.

Children are like clay waiting to be molded into their best shape and form. They are flexible in their thinking while their bodies are still growing and open to change. Exercise and its importance cannot be overstated. It is very important for everyone, regardless of age and gender. In fact, the more physically active a child is, the better he or she will perform in other areas of life. In general, the word "aerobic" refers to free oxygen in the air. This means that aerobic exercises are cardio exercises that improve heart rate and better perform respiratory functions in the body. Aerobic exercise can be adapted to various forms and benefits the human body in many ways. There are a variety of sports that kids can choose from such as football, basketball, hockey, ice skating and so on. In fact, studies have shown that children who play at least one sport get sick less often because of a stronger immune system. They also perform better academically because their brains get constant circulation. They develop lovable personalities because playing sports involves teamwork and coordination to help them learn to live with others.

It's not always easy to get kids involved in aerobic dance for kids if they don't like dancing themselves, but it has many benefits, such as flexibility, motor skills, and limb strength. They can learn dance that includes aerobic steps for children. Regardless of the form of dance, dancing itself is a very effective exercise that tones the body and improves fluidity of movement in the limbs. It is also believed that children who regularly dance and listen to music have a calmer mind and are emotionally developed due to the release of serotonin in the body. The benefits of swimming during childhood, during the formation of the locomotor system and the body as a whole, are very high. This sport, like no other, increases the capabilities of the respiratory system and develops absolutely all muscles. Children enjoy visiting the pool, combining positive emotions and health benefits. During swimming, all muscle groups are developed, because the participation of each muscle is necessary to keep the body on the surface of the water. The level of physical activity depends on the type of swimming chosen, whether it is breaststroke, front crawl or butterfly.

The load received during training helps to increase not only strength, but also the endurance of muscle tissue.

Exercising in the pool is the best way to regain lost shape or get a developed muscle corset without affecting the joints and intervertebral discs.

Activities performed during training in the pool are safer than in the gym, because the water cools the body, and the alternating tension and relaxation of the muscles leads to a decrease in the level of fatigue.

Water aerobics is one of the most effective types of aerobics, it helps muscle development, weight loss, good posture, joint mobility. Water aerobics is suitable for people of any age and fitness level, and has practically no contraindications. Water aerobics is a type of aerobics that involves performing exercises in water and combining physical activity in all the main muscle groups of a person, which is associated with high efficiency of training. In other words, aqua aerobics is artistic water gymnastics accompanied by music. Aqua aerobics is usually held in groups of 7-15 people. You can do it individually with a trainer, but such lessons are quite expensive. In order to maintain the rhythmic pace of the exercises, as well as to keep the students in a good mood, the lessons are accompanied by dance music.

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